

*Shifting Ruralities Symposium
Brussels, July 3rd-4th, 2025*

*Under Panel 4:
The Liveability of Rural Places
Design and Co-creation*

Title:

**Generic Houses
—Reusing Invisible Resources**

Pedro Duarte Bento ¹

Ph.D. in Architecture, Field of Theory and Practice of Project
Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade de Lisboa - Lisbon School of Architecture | Portugal
Email: pedroduarteporto@gmail.com | www.pedroduarteporto.com

Abstract (for Long-Form Paper)

During the third quarter of the 20th century, Portugal suffered a dwelling shortage. A series of socioeconomic, cultural and technological circumstances originated peculiar residential *New Vernacular* typologies —a process in which architects did not participate. Novel types, commonly called *emigrant-houses* and *clandestine-houses*, among others unspecified at the time —namely the *Generic House*, now identified—, started to populate the landscape, from suburban territories to rural areas. A *nouvelle-vague* of folk expression often stigmatized by the urban elites, characterized by hybrid morphologies, flawed interior organization, and poor thermal-acoustic comfort. This paper explores the hypothesis of reusing these deficient and ignored artifacts as a strategy to mitigate the present housing crisis. In a first moment by analyzing case-studies of plot densification, whereas in a collective approach as in DOGMA's *'The Opposite Shore'* series, or in a private one as *'Transformations Pavillonnaires'* illustrated. Secondly, using a renovation project for a *Generic House* type model, possible modifications and improvements are listed. From interior comfort to aesthetic conformity, from spatial re-organization to flexible utilization. Learning from this one example, a valuable method of retrofit and renovation can be traced, optimized with different solutions for different needs. And, in doing so, to create an opportunity for reusing at a larger scale a dismissed, *invisible resource*.

Keywords: *new vernacular; typology reuse; project strategy*
